

A Comparative Study of Managerial Talent of Professional versus Non-Professional Managers in Banking Sector

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Abstract- *The research paper focuses on the assessment of managerial talent in professional and non-professional managers. It also examines that whether the professional management education is proficient enough to produce such managerial competencies in individuals which contribute the most to success in organization or not. In order to achieve research objectives a sample of professional and non-professional managers was randomly selected from different regions of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The study sample consisted of 250 managers from selected banks. The number of questionnaire returned was 142 managers representing response rate of 56.8 percent. Data was analyzed by computing the corresponding means, standard deviations and the coefficients of variance for each of the group of the professional and non-professional managers using SPSS package. The result indicated that Non Professional managers exhibit reasonable social skills as they were capable enough to maintain a better relationship with customer and in team and people leadership. To some extent entrepreneurial characteristics in terms of ability to take risks, accepting challenges and availing opportunities seemed to be higher in Non Professional as compared to Professional ones. While on the other hand, the ability to analyze something observed to be higher in professional managers. Because they were proved to be better in taking good decisions, problem solving and managing change. The communication pattern of professional managers was also seemed to be better than non professional managers.*

Keyword: Professional, Non Professional, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, managerial talent

Introduction

In the ancient times the word talent referred to as expertise in any functional area with skills knowledge, competence or effectiveness to achieve predetermined targets. In nowadays, it is an increasing realization that it is not functional skills alone that matters but it also includes leadership qualities with the ability to straddle different functional areas, businesses, and cultures. In essence, talent in leaders refers to the ability to effectively handle competing imperatives. The relationship between the talent and organization's challenges, effective strategy execution requires adequate number of the right people with the right skills and knowledge in the right roles.

In nowadays the demand for talent becomes more challenging because of globalization, deregulation and rapid advances in technology. In the McKinsey & Co. surveys, in 2000, "99 percent of the corporate officers said that their managerial talent pools needed to be much stronger three years hence. Only 20 percent agreed that they have enough talented leaders to pursue their companies' business opportunities".

In the ObΠój and co surveys in 2006 demonstrated that "availability of managerial talent is the challenge most frequently cited in the human resources field. Seen as the biggest one by as many as 32% CEOs against 22% a year earlier, it clearly indicates a perceptible change in attitudes. Four years ago, human resources were seen as the least important among all potential concerns. Today's dynamics warrant the conclusion that, as predicted, such pattern of responses reflected temporary developments related to economic slowdown and a qualitatively new phenomenon, joblessness among key professionals and managers. But war for talent is back here and now, and in the years to come it may only intensify further".

The financial services sector has been subject to similar rapid environmental change due to the growth of new technology, the internationalization of trading and greater customer sophistication. The banking has become a complex activity within the financial market linked directly and indirectly with an over-all national growth and its impact as an integral part of regional segment of a global banking environment. Almost every bank and financial institution is involved in various functions in a today's job and thus requires a highly effective team and appropriate

manpower to run the show. In this context the assessment and development of managerial skills and competencies is likely to become even more important (Boam and Sparrow, 1992).

However, in Pakistan the banking sector has grown from a few institutions primarily involved in deposit acceptance and trade finance into a complex multi player markets where large number of commercial banks, financial institutions and specialized banks are operating with various products and activities. In such multifarious situation of banking sector, goals are translated into viable realities and profits only with human element that play their due role in achieving the desired results.

Thus, this research paper focused on assessment of managerial talent in banking sector specifically in the region of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Managers in banking sector were divided into 2 categories for the purposes of this study. These categories include; professionals possessing specialization in the field of management and non professionals, promoted on the base of their experience or having specialization in any other field except management. This study provides insight on managerial competencies in these two categories of managers and guidelines for developing a set of competencies in students during professional management education that should eventually lead to an increased individual productivity, higher compensation and faster improvement of their careers.

Literature Review

The productivity and efficiency of organizations have always depended heavily on the quality of their workforce, or their 'human capital', and there is general agreement that its importance relative to fixed capital is steadily increasing (Elias and Scarbrough, 2004).

Management development researchers maintain that there are three keys to developing managerial talent (Van Velsor, McCauley, & Moxley, 1998). According to them these are developmental work experiences, managerial ability to learn and supportive organizational context.

Developmental work experiences are important because they provide the challenge and the motivation necessary to improve skills and broaden perspectives. For over the past 20 years a considerable amount of research has been conducted to explore the work experiences that contribute to the development of managerial competencies (Kotter, 1982; McCall et al., 1988).

(McCauley et al.1994) call these features of assignments that provide challenge as the *developmental components* since they provide opportunities for learning new skills, behavior, and perspectives in situations that matter and are challenging, and they highlight developmental needs and indicate necessary capabilities to meet the role requirements of their assignment.

These components include *unfamiliar responsibilities*, which refers to the degree that a manager is expected to assume a set of new, different, or broader responsibilities. Job assignments that require managers to change work roles (e.g., switching from line to staff, changing employee status, receiving a significant increase in responsibility) have been identified as being developmental (McCall et al., 1988)

Creating change involves assignments that necessitate the implementation of change and can stem from multiple sources (McCauley et al., 1994). Some may come in the form of the manager being required to develop new directions through, for example, starting a new business unit, making strategic changes, implementing a reorganization, or reacting to a change in the business environment. Others may originate from having to address problems created by a predecessor or may involve attempting to carry out changes when employees are either resistant to change or lack the necessary knowledge or skills required for effective implementation.

The third developmental component of work experience involves assignments that provide a *high level of responsibility*. These include work experiences that provide the manager visibility with senior management and other influential executives and a broad set of responsibilities in terms of scale and scope (e.g., managing larger budgets, more people, and more diverse functions) can support motivation to enhance managerial skills and abilities and provide a forum for making an impact (McCall et al., 1988).

Managing interfaces, which come in the form of job assignments that require managers to develop strategies for influencing others, are another developmental work experience component. These types of work experiences may stem from having to coordinate with and/or depend on other departments or work units either inside or outside the organization (e.g., having to coordinate with suppliers or contractors). They can also involve situations where managers need to gain cooperation over those whom they have little formal authority (McCauley et al., 1994; Ohlott, 1998).

The final developmental component of managerial work experience is *managing diversity*. It comes in the form of assignments that require a manager to work across cultures (e.g., managing a demographically diverse work group). Assignments that contains these five components enables junior managers to develop the critical capabilities that translate into more effective thinking and action.

A second key factor in the development of managerial capabilities is the manager's ability to learn (Van Velsor et al., 1998). In the executive development literature, a manager's "ability to learn" is consistently mentioned as a key

characteristic for managers when it comes to developing from work experiences (McCauley, 2001). Although the ability to learn in managers is likely a complex combination of cognitive ability, personality, and learning tactics that may function in different capacities in relation to work experiences (Van Velsor et al., 1998).

In addition to developmental work experiences and managers' ability to learn, another key factor for developing managerial talent is a supportive organizational context (Van Velsor et al., 1998). While this can come in many forms, one key consideration is the degree to which managers have access to developmental assignments (McCauley, 2001).

Managerial talent is almost universally considered a critical ingredient to organizational success (Cappelli, 2000; Johnson, 2000; Michaels et al., 2001; Tulgan, 2001; Welch, 2001; Ashby and Miles, 2002; Bossidy and Charan, 2002; Pfau and Kay, 2002; Nalbantian, 2004). So, it should be developed in individuals to ensure organizational success. Now the question is, whether the professional management education is producing such managerial talent in individuals or not. The effectiveness of traditional MBA programmes has been criticized recently both in the US and in Europe, challenging business schools and asking for innovative strategies in graduate management education (Pfeffer and Fong, 2002). However, in context of Pakistan, Business schools in Pakistan are facing number of issues including lack of quality faculty, variable quality of business graduates, uncertain demand in the job market and lack of locally relevant research (Jamshed Hassan Khan 2006).

Methodology

A quantitative research method was employed to collect data from 250 managers which are randomly selected from banking sector in different regions of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The participants were encouraged to answer spontaneously and were assured of anonymity of answers. The number of questionnaire returned to the researcher was 142 managers representing response rate of 56.8 percent and these questionnaires were found to be suitable for data analysis. There were 66 professional and 66 non professional managers. The remaining questionnaire were discarded for different reasons such as missing more than 25 percent of data and ticking more than one answer for all questions. Following McCall et.al (1998), McCauley et.al (1994) and Van Velsor et.al (1998), the key variable for assessment of managerial talent in the study were achievement focus, change management, team and people leadership, communication, customer focus, problem solving and cost consciousness. All these variables provide a base for the development of managerial talent in individuals. In other words, these are the developmental components necessary for the growth of managerial talent in managers. A questionnaire based upon assessment of these variables on likert scale was used as a research instrument during the research. Subjects are asked to express agreement or disagreement of a six-point scale. Each degree of agreement is given a numerical value from one to six. Thus a total numerical value can be calculated from all the responses. Often the scale is: 1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Rather Disagree 4. Rather Agree 5. Agree 6. Strongly Agree

Results and Discussions

For this study the average, standard deviation and coefficients of variance was computed for each of the group of the professional and non professional managers. The conclusion was made initially on the basis of mean and standard deviation. Coefficient of Variance criteria was also used where decision was not clear on the basis of first two.

Achievement focus

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance

Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	4.7424	1.09980	1.210
	Disagree	4	6.1	6.1	6.1	-			
	R. Disagree	6	9.1	9.1	15.2	4.7424			
	R. Agree	8	12.1	12.1	27.3	-			
	Agree	33	50.0	50.0	77.3	-			
	S. Agree	15	22.7	22.7	100.0	-			
Total	66	100.0	100.0						
Professional managers	S. Disagree	6	9.1	9.1	9.1	4.5455	1.50058	2.252	
	Disagree	5	7.6	7.6	16.7				-
	R. Disagree	-	-	-	-				-
	R. Agree	5	7.6	7.6	24.2				4.5455
	Agree	36	54.5	54.5	78.8				-
	S. Agree	14	21.2	21.2	100.0				-
Total	66	100.0	100.0						

Results of the study reveals that non professional managers having high mean i.e. 4.742 and low standard deviation i.e. 1.0998 as compared to professional managers with mean of 4.546 and standard deviation of 1.501 possess the ample ability to accept the challenges by setting and achieving challenging goals more frequently than professional managers. This indicates that non professionals are proved to be self starters, willing to take calculated risk, avail opportunities and accept challenges of the future. So, Professional managers should try their best to bring up them to this level.

Change management

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	4.7121	1.22494	1.500
	Disagree	6	9.1	9.1	9.1			
	R. Disagree	6	9.1	9.1	18.2			
	R. Agree	7	10.6	10.6	28.8			
	Agree	29	43.9	43.9	72.7			
	S. Agree	18	27.3	27.3	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					
Professional managers	S. Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	1.5	4.9091	1.17313	1.376
	Disagree	5	7.6	7.6	9.1			
	R. Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	10.6			
	R. Agree	5	7.6	7.6	18.2			
	Agree	34	51.5	51.5	69.7			
	S. Agree	20	30.3	30.3	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					

From the above table it is clear that nonprofessional managers exhibit low mean of 4.71 and high standard deviation of 1.22 in contrast with professional managers having mean of 4.90 and standard deviation of 1.1. They are efficient in managing change by making workable implementation plans, having ability to communicate change effectively, building commitment and overcome resistance, providing support to affectees of change, monitoring and evaluation of results brought by change later on.

Team and people leadership

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
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Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	5.0909	0.87226	0.761
	Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	1.5			
	R. Disagree	3	4.5	4.5	6.1			
	R. Agree	7	10.6	10.6	16.7			
	Agree	33	50.0	50.0	66.7			
	S. Agree	22	33.3	33.3	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					
Professional managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	5.0000	1.12318	1.262
	Disagree	3	4.5	4.5	4.5			
	R. Disagree	5	7.6	7.6	12.1			
	R. Agree	8	12.1	12.1	24.2			
	Agree	23	34.8	34.8	59.1			
	S. Agree	27	40.9	40.9	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					

The above table reveals that non professionals with high mean (5.09) and low standard deviation (0.872) are comparatively better in gaining cooperation and providing direction to others than professionals having mean of 5.00 and standard deviation of 1.12. In other words they are better able to create an environment which allows individuals to reach their full potential. Thus leadership qualities are proved to be higher in non professional than professional managers. Non professional managers are good in gaining cooperation and providing direction to others, group problem solving, giving them opportunity to develop skills, acknowledging and appraising team and individual accomplishments. While on the other hand, professional managers' scores lesser on these aspects of leadership. Therefore professional managers need to focus on above mentioned leadership qualities to be good managers.

Communication

		Frequ ency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	4.6515	1.44107	2.077
	Disagree	5	7.6	7.6	7.6			
	R. Disagree	17	25.8	25.8	33.3			
	R. Agree	2	3.0	3.0	36.4			
	Agree	14	21.2	21.2	57.6			
	S. Agree	28	42.4	42.4	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					
Professional managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	4.7879	1.01550	1.031
	Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	1.5			
	R. Disagree	8	12.1	12.1	13.6			
	R. Agree	12	18.2	18.2	31.8			
	Agree	28	42.4	42.4	74.2			
	S. Agree	17	25.8	25.8	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					

As far as communication pattern is concerned, the greater mean i.e. 4.7 and low standard deviation i.e. 1.0155 in professional managers indicates that they are better in communication as compared to non professional managers with a mean and standard deviation of 4.65 and 1.44 respectively. Thus the communication pattern of professional

is better than non professional managers. Professional managers have proficiency in abilities of verbal and written communication, listening and comprehension, keeping other adequately informed as compared to non professionals.

Customer focus

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	5.4394	0.55826	0.312
	Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Agree	2	3.0	3.0	3.0			
	Agree	33	50.0	50.0	53.0			
	S. Agree	31	47.0	47.0	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					
Professional managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	5.4545	0.63686	0.406
	Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Agree	5	7.6	7.6	7.6			
	Agree	26	39.4	39.4	47.0			
	S. Agree	35	53.0	53.0	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					

Results in above table indicate that both categories of professional and non professional managers have equal mean i.e.5.4 but the standard deviation of non professional manager i.e.0.55826 is lower than professional managers which show standard deviation of 0.63686.Thus non professional managers are more efficient in maintaining valuable relationship with customers than professional ones. Professional managers should make appropriate efforts to improve their relations with customers. It is necessary to gain their trust and respect.

Problem solving

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Coefficient of variance
Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	4.5758	0.9124	0.833	19.941
	Disagree	-	-	-	-				
	R. Disagree	6	9.1	9.1	9.1				
	R. Agree	29	43.9	43.9	53.0				
	Agree	18	27.3	27.3	80.3				
	S. Agree	13	19.7	19.7	100.0				
Total	66	100.0	100.0						
Professional managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	4.8030	0.94819	0.899	19.741
	Disagree	-	-	-	-				
	R. Disagree	8	12.1	12.1	12.1				
	R. Agree	13	19.7	19.7	31.8				
	Agree	29	43.9	43.9	75.8				
	S. Agree	16	24.2	24.2	100.0				
Total	66	100.0	100.0						

The above table demonstrates that mean (4.8030) and standard deviation (0.94819) of professional managers is greater than non professional ones having mean and standard deviation of 4.5758 and 0.91249 respectively. Therefore, in order to find out which is best in solving the problem in time, the coefficient of variance is calculated. The low coefficient of variance of professional managers (19.741) as compared to non professionals having

coefficient of variance of 19.941 indicates that they exhibit ability to solve problem in time. Professional manager are efficient in identifying problem in time, analyzing information and developing alternative solution. They exhibit ability to solve problem in early stage. On the other hand, non professional scores less on all these aspects of solving problem efficiently.

Cost consciousness

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Non Professional Managers	S. Disagree	-	-	-	-	4.8333	0.8697	0.756
	Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Disagree	5	7.6	7.6	7.6			
	R. Agree	16	24.2	24.2	31.8			
	Agree	30	45.5	45.5	77.3			
	S. Agree	15	22.7	22.7	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					
Professional managers	S. Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	1.5	4.8939	0.8436	0.712
	Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Disagree	-	-	-	-			
	R. Agree	17	25.8	25.8	27.3			
	Agree	34	51.5	51.5	78.8			
	S. Agree	14	21.2	21.2	100.0			
Total	66	100.0	100.0					

Results in above table show that professional managers have high mean i.e.4.89 and low standard deviation i.e. 0.8436, as compared to non professional managers possessing mean of 4.83 and standard deviation of 0.860. These results indicate that professional managers are better in having capacity to work within approved budget. Although, both categories of managers try their best to work within approved budget, by developing cost saving measures but professional managers are seemed to be a little bit better in doing so.

Conclusion

The results of the study revealed that non professional managers needs intense progress in the acquisition of skills like problem solving, managing change, process management and communication. While on the other hand professional managers, being professionally qualified have grip upon the developmental components of managerial talent such as problem solving, managing change, and communication. These competencies enable professional managers to develop the critical capabilities that translate into more effective thinking and action. As a result they are better able to set and implement agendas, and develop a strong sense of self-awareness, basic values, and temperament that guide and direct behavior.

Hence, professional managers experiencing these developmental components of managerial talent indicate higher levels of on-the-job learning and their jobs contribute more towards managerial development than non professionals who report experiencing these developmental components to a lesser degree. However, professional managers should concentrate little bit upon maintaining long term relationship with customers and team and people leadership.

On the basis of all these observations it is recommended that management education should focus on inculcating interpersonal and social skills in students so that they can be able to develop long term relationship and practical training skills with internal and external customers of the organization. Furthermore universities should work closely with the Industry Associations such as Pakistan Banks Association to revise the curriculum, attract qualified faculty and instructional staff, and modify the testing and examination methodology to produce the required number and quality of graduates. Such graduates should be recruited on merit through a highly competitive process and offer short courses for non professional managers to update their knowledge about the managerial skills and competencies.

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